

Post-Experiment Questionnaire

1. How confident do you feel about your answers in Part 1: Structure Comprehension?
1 (not confident at all) 5 (extremely confident)
2. How confident do you feel about your answers in Part 2: Behavior Comprehension?
1 (not confident at all) 5 (extremely confident)
3. How effective do you think the tool (Visual Paradigm or Eclipse) was in helping you understand the software?
1 (not effective at all) 5 (extremely effective)
4. How effective do you think the provided artifacts (UML models or code) were in helping you understand the software?
1 (not effective at all) 5 (extremely effective)
5. Please provide any feedback on the task, the artifacts, the tool, etc.